

Religion in the Old Assyrian Period

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The Old Assyrian period refers to the earliest attested period of the city of Assur in the north of modern-day Iraq, later the cultural center of the regionally dominant Assyrian empire. In the opening centuries of the 2nd millennium, Assur was a single city-state ruled by a representative council, whose economic engine was long distance trade in tin and textiles to Anatolia (modern-day Turkey). The extreme profitability of the trade led several generations of Assyrian merchants to settle full-time in the Anatolian city of Kanesh, where they established a community referred to as the "port" with its own representative body to govern the local Assyrian community. The Old Assyrian pantheon was largely identical with that of the rest of Mesopotamia, with the exception of the chief god of the city. The city-god of Assur bore the same name as the city itself (modern scholars sometimes use "Ashur" for the god in order to distinguish the two, but the native writing was identical); for the Assyrians, Ashur was the chief god of the larger pantheon. The Ashur cult and its large temple environs were the center of polity life at Assur, which seems to have lacked a palace for most of the period. Second to the Ashur cult was that of the goddess Ishtar Assuritunga, who also had a large temple complex at the city. Smaller temples of other important deities existed, and certainly myriad gods had shrines within the larger temple complexes. While naturally the Assyrian merchants did not have monumental temple complexes in their Anatolian host cities, the evidence makes clear that shrines to the many Assyrian gods were established at Kanesh and elsewhere, and some Assyrians served as priests in the "port". What we know of religion in the Old Assyrian period is heavily circumscribed by our evidence, which comes predominately from the massive textual and archaeological corpus left behind by the merchants at the site of ancient Kanesh, supplemented by some archaeological evidence from the hometown of Assur itself. Consequently, what is commonly called "Old Assyrian Religion" is above-all the lived religious experience of a group of one thousand or so individuals comprised of Assyrian merchants and their networks of relations. Furthermore, the great bulk of written evidence is from a 30-year window circa 1895-1865. Therefore, even though our window into "Old Assyrian Religion" is narrow and incomplete, it is near-unique for the ancient world in its intimacy.

Date Range: 1972 BCE - 1718 BCE

Region: The City-State of Assur and Assyrian Communities in Anatolia

Region tags: Middle East, Northern Iraq, Turkey, Anatolia, Northern Mesopotamia

The center of gravity for Old Assyrian period religion is the city-state of Assur in northern Iraq, but the economic engine of the city-state was long-distance trade and thus the home of many of its people was Kanesh in Anatolia, and indeed the majority of our evidence for religious practice (both at home and abroad) comes from Kanesh. Old Assyrian society existed in dialogue between these two points. The region for OA religion must necessarily be both Assur the city and the permanent Assyrian merchant communities in Anatolia (above all the lower town at Kanesh).

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hirsch, Hans. *Untersuchungen zur altassyrischen Religion*. Osnabrück: Biblio Verlag, 1972.
- Source 2: Veenhof, Klaas R. and Jesper Eidem. *Mesopotamia: The Old Assyrian Period*. Fribourg: Academic Press, 2008.
- Source 3: Larsen, Mogens Trolle. *Ancient Kanesh: A Merchant Colony in Bronze Age Anatolia*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.metmuseum.org/toah/hd/assy_2/hd_assy_2.htm
- Source 1 Description: A basic but good introduction to the Old Assyrian period, with an emphasis on art history
- Source 2 URL: https://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/doku.php?id=old_assyrian_letters
- Source 2 Description: An overview of Old Assyrian letter writing, from which come much of the evidence for religion. Also includes a helpful link to all the transliterated letters available on the CDLI database.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://oare.byu.edu>
- Source 1 Description: The Old Assyrian Research Environment (OARE) is an under-construction database of all published Old Assyrian texts in transliteration. In some instances translation and grammatical analysis are available, and the database is being rapidly built out.
- Source 2 URL: <https://cdli.ucla.edu>
- Source 2 Description: The Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI) has a more limited selection of transliterations of Old Assyrian texts, but is the largest online database of cuneiform texts in general. Many of the Old Assyrian texts in the database include not only transliteration but also high-resolution digital photos of the tablets.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

- No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: While "pluralistic" is perhaps not a helpful term for describing the interactions of polytheistic systems, it is certainly true that the contact between the Assyrians and local Anatolians involved accommodation. There is evidence for Assyrian participation in the cult of Anna, the city-goddess of Kanesh. And while there is no evidence for direct Assyrian participation in other Anatolian cults, both Assyrian and Anatolian gods regularly interact in various spheres: for example, as divine witnesses in legal proceedings involving both Assyrians and Anatolians and as participants in treaties.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: It is highly unlikely that the ancient Assyrians or Anatolians had any concept of their "religion" as a discrete sphere of life, much less that they assigned "religious affiliation" to individuals or groups. However, they certainly recognized that the Assyrians and Anatolians worshipped a different selection of gods, and their identity as Assyrians is intimately tied up in their connection the eponymous city-god Assur.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: While it is perhaps artificial to describe the Assyrian and Anatolian religious world as discrete "religions", it is certainly the case that 100% of the Assyrian population revered the gods of the city of Assur, while the local Anatolians revered their own deities.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious

monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: The Assyrians buried their dead under the floors. While these burials would hardly qualify as monumental, they certainly were centers of religious practice: the dead under the floor were cared for with regular food and drink offerings, and the spirits of the ancestors were potent forces for both benefice and malice among the living.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: While "altar" is likely not the best term, there were clearly household shrines, perhaps

connected with the hearth of the home, that served a role in household religion. Furthermore, while the Assyrian gods had temples at the hometown of Assur (or else shrines within larger temples, in the case of minor deities), in Kanesh the "temples" of the Assyrian gods were almost certainly shrines, quite possibly connected with the homes of the individuals who served as their priests in Kanesh.

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: At Assur, the delineation between "cultic" and "political" space is hazy if it existed at all. There may have been no royal palace at Assur, and it is unclear where the ruler lived or had the center of his power. Much of the political power was in the hands of the democratic assembly of the "Large and Small" men of the city, and they likely met in a large space adjacent to the Ashur temple. In Kanesh, legal proceedings are typically recorded as occurring in the "gate of the god", where apparently the dagger of the god Ashur was kept in order to be brought out for swearing ceremonies.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

Notes: This is hard to answer, as there is no "doctrine" per-se for the Assyrians. Certainly the iconography of cylinder seals, for example, depicts libations and obeisance to various deities.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The city-god of Assur bore the same name as the city (although modern scholars often write the name of the god as "Ashur" to distinguish the two). Across Mesopotamia generally, city-gods were given an elevated status by the citizens of their towns. In the case of Ashur, however, the Assyrians treated their city-god as the true head of the divine pantheon, analogous to Enlil in the rest of Mesopotamia. The personality of Ashur as a deity in the Old Assyrian period is unclear, despite his extreme prominence in every facet of Assyrian life. He was likely associated with the rocky outcrop on and around which the city was built. Probable images of Ashur on cylinder seals can depict him as a mountain with the head and legs of a bull, while elsewhere he is depicted anthropomorphically. While in later periods Ashur's temple was uniquely at Assur (most Mesopotamian gods had multiple temples and shrines in various cities), in the Old Assyrian period additional shrines and even cult images were established in the Assyrian communities at Anatolia. Particularly important, from a legal perspective, was the dagger of Ashur; copies of this implement were used in oath ceremonies, where the dagger represents Ashur's presence as a witness of the oaths made.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: I'm not sure there's really a clear moral evaluation of deities, but certainly Ashur is never described as malevolent (though perhaps destructive, of course), and he is consistently worthy of service.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The god and city of Assur are not only coterminous but probably identified. The god Assur is likely originally the deified city, and he can be presented as anthropomorphic but also as a mountain with a bull head and legs, likely representing the rock mountain on and around which the city is built.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Apparently the gods' knowledge is comprehensive
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Direct afflictions by demons or the spirits of the dead, such as by an individual falling sick, are often interpreted as communication from Assur or other deities.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination processes:
– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Household calamity and bodily affliction may be attributable to spirits

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally

visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Supernatural beings that are neither gods nor spirits of the dead appear most often as protective or vindictive beings, and most often are deputized by the gods.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: While divinized kings or ancestors are a feature of Mesopotamian religion broadly, those elements are subdued in the Old Assyrian evidence we possess.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: This is often true (storm-gods, sun-god, etc.) but not universally. Many gods don't have a "domain" per se, but several areas of expertise or no identifiable ones at all.

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The inter cella of temples were only accessible to those functionaries who had tasks there: clothing and feeding the gods, caring for their images, etc. However, there is little Old Assyrian evidence for these exclusive realms, and while logically one might suppose the god himself/herself is thought to not want just anyone in their cella, there is no evidence making that explicit.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: The gods have sacred objects that represent them in swearing oaths, etc. Special care is certainly given them, but there is no direct evidence for how the god perceives their mishandling.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Bestiality forbidden
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - No

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is complicated. I wouldn't say it is rather a case of "religion" extending its norms into all

areas of life rather than that "social norms" are formed in a society that includes both human and non-human social actors, and so inevitably social norms are shaped by gods, spirits, and demons in much the same way they're shaped by humans.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: This largely depends on the circumstance and the norm. But certainly some laws, promulgated by the king, are described as handed down as just laws from the gods.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Yes

Notes: This is complicated and depends largely what you mean by the metaphysical. Moral norms are derived and enforced by both human and non-human actors (deities included). There doesn't seem to be much emphasis on moral norms as existing in some abstract sense, but rather as being tied to relationship: both human and divine.

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
- All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Obviously to be Assyrian did not require celibacy. However, there were female priests dedicated to various deities in Mesopotamia, and it is certain that many of these women were not allowed to marry and probable that they were not allowed to be sexually active. Many Assyrians dedicated their daughters as priestesses of Assur, and it seems that these priestesses were similar to their Mesopotamian analogues in their marital and sexual status.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her

actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Votive gifts and food offerings were regularly given to the gods, offerings made to the dead, and a common social activity appears to have involved giving small monetary gifts to acquaintances called "sacrifices", presumably then used to purchase a small animal for sacrifice to the gods.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: Destroyed in the sense of animal or food sacrifice, though some portion of each may have been eaten by the giver and/or officiants as well.

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: This may be minimal compared to sacrifice of material goods. But certainly periodic rituals, etc. required some time.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: To be clear, no Assyrian was NOT a part of this religious group, so while being Assyrian included ethical obligations enforced by human and divine alike, probably no one was conscious of accepting these precepts as something distinctly "religious"

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This probably differed wildly depending on station. But for the "average" person the performance of rituals was not likely a large time consumer.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know little about the temples in Assur. Certainly periods of shortage occurred, and texts from the city to the merchants in Kanesh mention famine. In other places, the temples often offered small loans for purchase of seed or food in times of hardship, and it is likely (but not currently demonstrable) that the temples in Assur during this period did the same.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As noted regarding famine, temples in Mesopotamia appear to have provided loans and resources for periods of hardship. The Assur temples likely did the same but our texts do not show it.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Certainly the temples employed scribes and probably trained them as well, but education was not a general part of their work

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: This largely depends what you mean. There is evidence that individuals could acquire the technology of writing, for example, and that some women may have written for themselves. But there is no real evidence for formal education in a dedicated institution (except perhaps for scribal training for political or cultic purposes).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is mention of "collections" being made, but it is not clear if it is obligatory.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Notes: This is not clear. Certainly the judges serve the gods and rely on their witness for ratifying judgment, but it's not clear who appoints the judges. They are part of this religious world, but probably not appointed directly by the temple household, for instance.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: This is, again, complicated on a categorical level. The Assyrian merchants were not affiliates of a religious group while also participants in a polity. These are all of a piece and not meaningfully differentiated conceptually. The temples don't seem to have run the military, but if the "religious group" is all the "sons and daughters of Assur" (citizens of the city), then this organization with the god Assur at its head indeed had a military corps.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

- ↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:
- Patoralism
 - Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)